

TOP 15 COMMODITIES EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Exports have played an increasingly important role in India's economic growth in the last two decades. This paper analyses the performance of India's exports and the various economic factors which have contributed to its growth. The study about which commodity will highly export from India to other countries.

Key Words: Fresh Fruits and Vegetables Products, Export and Data

Introduction:

Export is playing a major role of development and growth of the countries. Exports are goods and services that are produced in one country and sold to buyers in another. Exports are incredibly important to modern economies because they offer people and firms many more markets for their goods. One of the core functions of diplomacy and foreign policy between governments is to foster economic trade, encouraging exports and imports for the benefit of all trading parties. India's diverse climate ensures availability of all varieties of fresh fruits & vegetables. It ranks second in fruits and vegetables production in the world, after China. As per National Horticulture Database (Second Advance Estimates) published by National Horticulture Board, during 2019-20, India produced 99.07 million metric tons of fruits and 191.77 million metric tons of vegetables. The area under cultivation of fruits stood at 6.66 million hectares while vegetables were cultivated at 10.35 million hectares.

Problem Statement:

- The potential for cultivating fruits and vegetables from domestic and export market is high.
- Despite the being the healthy demand for Indian fruits and vegetables abroad.
- The country faces the serious problems with finding exportable quality fruits and vegetables in sufficient amount.

Objectives of the Study:

- To assess the exporting details of fresh fruits and vegetables to the top 10 countries in exports.
- To provide necessary suggestion based on the findings of the study.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the project is involved the export performance Fresh Fruits and Vegetables the export performance of Indian Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products is affected by the high demand. The study also gives growth rate and trend percentage of the export of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables goods year wise and also country wise. The study provides suggestion to the Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products exporting industries to improve their performance.

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

Secondary data the secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, publication of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products in the website of India Export Statistics-APEDA and industries, bulletins working and occasional papers of foreign trade preference analysis were used as important sources of secondary data for the study.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis made only by considering 12 Fresh Fruits and Vegetables products and 10 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limitations.

Period of Study:

The research data is collected in 12 financial years. That year is 2010-11 to 2021-22.

Review of Literature:

Mathor and Sagar (2015) state that the exports are increasing at a decreasing rate but the imports are increasing at an increasing rate. Trade deficit increased very sharply from 2004-05 to 2009- 10. The composition of India & #39s foreign trades has undergone substantial changes, particularly, after the liberalization and globalization. Our major exports now includes manufacturing goods such as Engineering Goods, Petroleum Products, Chemicals and allied Products, Gems and Jewelleries, Textiles, Electronic Goods, etc. India's Exports of Services Important: Since data below is for latest time period hence data above too should be of same period so as to maintain consistency. It is a remarkable achievement that we have transformed

ourselves from a predominantly primary goods exporting country into a non-primary goods (manufactured goods) exporting country. By exploiting the benefit of GATS now India is becoming the largest exporter of services.

Sahni (2014): The changing structure of India's exports throws some interesting light on both the demand pattern and supply factors that are increasingly influencing India's exports and the manner in which its production structures, institutions, and policies are responding to it. Regarding changes in the composition of exports since 1980s, it may be observed that the share of agriculture and allied products has been declining while that of ores and minerals has remained more or less steady. Share of manufactured goods has increased generally. Although the opening up of the Indian economy since the early 1990s provided impetus for higher growth for most of the commodities, some products gained more than the others. India's merchandise exports are predominated by the manufacturing sector which accounted for more than three fourth of its total exports during post-reform period.

Bhat (2011) reported that the post reform period in India has witnessed significant changes in the trend, pattern and structure of external trade. The share of manufacturing sector has marginally fallen in the GDP and significantly declined in the share of export. The growth of services was more pronounced in GDP growth and is reflected in the increasing share of services in exports. The share of primary products has fallen in export and that of petroleum products showed an increase. The author hence reported that in near future India may emerge as an 'Asian Petroleum Hub. He further remarked that India has not taken the advantage of international segmentation of production process and the export is still heavily dominated by labour intensive products characterized by a slow growing international demand and protected markets.

Export of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables in India:

Table 1

Values in Lacs

Year	Australia	Growth Rate	USA	Growth Rate	Belgium	Growth Rate	Canada	Growth Rate	Indonesia	Growth Rate
2009	23501.56		187651.4		18301.67		29739.97		75085.94	
2010	26270.89	111.65	349715	86.36	17651.47	-3.55	33665.98	13.2	172793.58	130.13
2011	62436.36	237.54	1467341	319.58	33023.38	87.09	73187.39	117.39	381441.42	120.75
2012	76997.22	123.27	2024960	38	50276.84	52.25	90274.31	23.35	490930.42	28.7
2013	65892.15	85.54	1210281	-40.23	52082.03	3.59	86520.69	-4.16	433889.12	-11.62
2014	74196.78	112.55	1091363	-9.83	49644.98	-4.68	104713.45	21.03	369583.1	-14.82
2015	72044.97	97.06	617038.4	-43.46	49745.88	0.2	86134.63	-17.74	178367.04	-51.74
2016	78151.6	108.43	727604	17.92	67711.89	36.12	87687.2	1.8	347827.08	95.01
2017	94683.64	121.11	828221.2	13.83	73845.4	9.06	110862.21	26.43	267100.2	-23.21
2018	111768.1	118.01	852192.5	2.89	67037.88	-9.22	124782.79	12.56	523706.31	96.07
2019	122289.7	109.39	758525.5	-10.99	33504.58	-50.02	142444.74	14.15	390472.21	-25.44
2020	161552.5	132.08	830347.2	9.47	37046.71	10.57	182522.45	28.14	512657.82	31.29
2021	132282	81.86	829753.6	-0.07	32904.85	-11.18	155426.87	-14.85	681297.03	32.9
Total	1102067		11774994		582777.56		1307962.7		4825151.3	
Average	84774.42		905768.8		44829.04		100612.51		371165.48	
(Source In India Export Statistics-Apeda)										
Trend Analysis										
2022	151480.3		858627.7		56305.84		174097.72		567923.36	
2023	159954.6		706023.2		54735.75		183079.22		571525.87	
2024	165075.8		511822.9		51095.81		190027.03		576071.49	
2025	178968.8		459092.4		47865.71		200966.25		606804.49	
2026	195268.1		534122.4		46264.61		214063.49		660563.6	
Export of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables in India										

Table 2

Values in Lacs

Year	Philippines	Growth Rate	Japan	Growth Rate	Saudi Arab	Growth Rate	Singapore	Growth Rate	Malaysia	Growth Rate
2009	81620.91		14428.75		453250.57		29124.36		206708.85	
2010	89142.62	9.22	15450.99	7.08	463055.83	2.16	30473.78	4.63	287291.56	38.98
2011	104316.39	17.02	23475.48	51.94	557076.13	20.3	54967.83	80.38	376833.29	31.17
2012	175904.84	68.63	30125.21	28.33	656641.09	17.87	90121.51	63.95	495146.48	31.4
2013	154217.86	-12.33	43643.25	44.87	1066563.7	62.43	112788.82	25.15	546724.53	10.42
2014	163596.92	6.08	43019.4	-1.43	1115023.5	4.54	124466.13	10.35	480143.69	-12.18
2015	154307.54	-5.68	41787	-2.86	916053.79	-17.84	125972.25	1.21	468536.05	-2.42
2016	152191.99	-1.37	70867.59	69.59	815320.29	-11	117024.52	-7.1	421997.42	-9.93
2017	150247.58	-1.28	91471.99	29.07	865070.99	6.1	112145.94	-4.17	419530.95	-0.58
2018	200687.43	33.57	95343.86	4.23	1013063.8	17.11	117000.26	4.33	459373.86	9.5
2019	128572.22	-35.93	80930.06	-15.12	1005501.4	-0.75	122793.24	4.95	462848.4	0.76
2020	162551.31	26.43	73249.67	-9.49	1064813.3	5.9	141863.23	15.53	653519.4	41.2
2021	282837.44	74	74260.49	1.38	725747.59	-31.84	129118.57	-8.98	707540.33	8.27
Total	2000195.1		698053.7		10717182		1307860.4		5986194.8	
Average	153861.16		53696.44		824398.62		100604.65		460476.52	
(Source In India Export Statistics-Apeda)										
Trend Analysis										
2022	220259.94		99733.51		1086092.9		158301.69		643566.42	
2023	226797.97		106347.3		1095239.5		162308.41		651100.29	
2024	231461.93		111911.7		1084746.1		162839.12		659646.75	
2025	235184.54		117235.4		1064790		163172.96		674049.8	

2026	248929.37		122074.6		1037545.7		166220.94		704759.65
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Interpretation:

The Fresh Fruits and Vegetables export from India to Australia during the year of 2009 to 2021. It achieved highest value in the year of 2020 was Rs 161552.5 lakhs. From growth rate analysis the Australia has achieved 13 years positive growth rate and remaining. While computing trend analysis to Fresh Fruits and Vegetables for upcoming five years, it clearly shows export of Fresh Fruits and Vegetables to the Australia will be increasing. Then India to USA growth rate 7 years are positive remaining years are negative growth rate. The trend analysis of USA'S upcoming 5 years are decreasing. Next India to Belgium growth rate 7 years is positive and remaining years are negative growth rate. The trend analysis of Belgium upcoming 5 years are decreasing. India to Canada growth rate 9 years positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Canada upcoming 5 years are increasing. And India to Indonesia growth rate 7 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Indonesia upcoming 5 years is increasing. Then India to Philippines growth rate are 7 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Philippines upcoming 5 years are increasing. India to Japangrowth rate is 8 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Japan upcoming 5 years is increasing. India to SAUDI Arab growth rate is 8 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of SAUDI Arab's upcoming 5 years are decreasing. India to Singapore growth rate are 9 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Singapore upcoming 5 years is increasing. And India to Malaysia's growth rate is 8 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Malaysia's upcoming 5 years is increasing.

Findings:

- The Fresh fruits and vegetables export from India to Australia high growth rate value is 237.54. That year is 2011. India to USA high growth rate value is 319.58. That year is 2011. India to Belgium high growth rate value is 87.09. That year is 2011.
- India to Canada high growth rate value is 117.39. That year is 2011. And India to Indonesia high growth rate value is 130.13. That year is 2010.
- Fresh fruits and Vegetables exports from India to other countries are trend analysis of upcoming 5 years is highly increasing.
- The India to Philippines high growth rate value is 74.00. That year is 2021. India to Japan high growth rate value is 69.59. That year is 2016. India to Saudi Arab high growth rate value is 62.43. That year is 2013.
- India to Singapore high growth rate value is 80.38. That year is 2011. And India to Malaysia high growth rate value is 41.20. That year is 2020.
- Fresh Fruits and Vegetables exports from India to other countries are trend analysis of upcoming 5 years is highly increasing.

Suggestions:

- Export strategies should be based on an assessment of your own position and research into promising opportunities. So want to know about the export strategies.
- The government should pay more attention to export these products in large quantities.

Conclusion:

In this case the top 12 commodities exports from India will studied. To know about the India's exporting data. This study will using methodology of secondary data, and that data collected in India export statistics- APEDA web page. In this case to find out the trend analysis. Most of products will make a many negative growth rate, so it's likely change in the near future. So, these of above things are studied in this component.

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